

EFFECTIVE READING STRATEGIES FOR DEVELOPING READING SKILLS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5901899>

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Annotation: *This article analyzes how to develop effective reading strategies in second language teaching and learning process. The reader will be aware of a wide range of reading strategies and how to deal with difficulties in language learning path. There are some useful reading tactics and strategies in this study which will be helpful in improving reading comprehension skill as well.*

Key words: *Reading strategies, Linguistic competence, Discourse competence, Sociolinguistic competency, Strategic competence*

Introduction. Millions of learners throughout the world are prioritizing the acquisition of reading skills in a second or foreign language, and there is a growing demand for both effective reading courses and high-quality second language reading materials. This comprehensive introduction to the teaching of second language reading will be welcomed by anybody interested in teaching reading or teacher education for language teachers. It is true that, reading skill has variety of ways for achieving the goal of reading. "The goals of the reading program," according to Nuttal (2005), "are to enable students to enjoy reading in the foreign language, and to read unfamiliar materials without assistance, at a suitable speed, silently, and with adequate understanding." However, in recent years, researchers have uncovered a wealth of information regarding reading strategies. This research examines the tactics of two authors, Luis (2007) and Pinnel, Su, and Foutas (1996). Pints also indicate which of these tactics is most appropriate for teaching reading as one of today's language skills.

What is reading? As we all know, teachers use a variety of approaches to teach English as a second language in order to help pupils speak and write fluently, as well as grasp the material. "Language skills" is the name given to them (listening, reading, speaking and writing). Language skills include the ability to read. "Reading is an interactive process that occurs between the reader and the text, culminating in comprehension," writes

Brynes (1998, 2). The meaning is encoded in the text through letters, phrases, and paragraphs." Reading, according to Brynes (1998, 2), can be a linguistic talent or a process that requires the reader to employ knowledge, abilities, and tactics.

1. Linguistic competence is defined as the capacity to recognize the parts of the writing system; vocabulary comprehension is defined as the understanding of how words are organized into sentences.

2. Discourse competence is the understanding of discourse markers and how they connect different parts of the text.

3. Sociolinguistic competence is defined as understanding of many types of writings, as well as their typical structure and content.

4. Strategic competence entails the capacity to employ top-down methods as well as linguistic proficiency (Bryners 1998, 2).

Furthermore, the aim of reading and the type of text is to identify the precise knowledge, abilities, and techniques that the reader will need to apply in order to attain reading comprehension. Because reading comprehension is more than decoding, it occurs when the reader understands which skills and methods are appropriate for the type of text and how to connect them to achieve the reading goal (Bryners 1998, 2).

The use of reading strategies. Before we go into the strategies, it's important to understand why they're utilized and when they're employed. Both of these questions are important for teachers to consider while teaching reading in an ESL classroom. We employ strategies for the following reasons, according to Sarasota (2001, 1):

1. When techniques are applied, reading makes better sense for struggling readers. 2. Good readers instinctively apply tactics.

3. Using strategies helps struggling readers improve their reading skills.

4. Strategies make reading more enjoyable.

People are wondering when are the strategies used? It is answered by Sarasota's (2001, 1) statement:

Students are helped by strategies in the following areas:

1. Predicting outcomes in a reading passage

2. Making a summary of what you've read, both fictional and nonfictional

3. Questioning what they're reading 4. Identifying key ideas as they read 5. Keeping track of what they're reading

6. Looking for clues

7. Confirming reading

8. Looking for signs in the head or back

Reading strategies. Reading practices that are effective help students read more efficiently. The student's goal with these tactics is to get the most out of their reading with the least amount of work. Many studies have been done on reading strategies.

This paper will look at the tactics used by Luis (2007) and Pinnel, Su, and Foutas (1996). According to Luis, there are six tactics to use while teaching reading in an ESL classroom. They are:

1. Having a clear idea of what you want to learn.

It's important to understand why you're reading the content.

What do you want to know now that you've finished reading it?

Are you reading for a specific reason or just for fun? If you know this, you can evaluate the text to see if it will help you achieve your goal. Examining the introduction and chapter headings is a straightforward way to do this. The introduction should state who the book is aimed at and what it aims to accomplish.

The chapter headers will provide you with an overview of the subject's structure.

Examine the book to see if it matches your requirements.

Examine whether it makes too many or too few assumptions.

Is it better to find another one if the book isn't a good deal?

2. Knowing how to study the material thoroughly

You can skim stuff if you simply need a basic understanding of the subject.

Only the chapter titles, introductions, and summaries are read here.

You can scan the text if you only require a moderate amount of information about a topic. In this section, you can read the introductions and summaries in depth. Then you may fast read the chapters' contents, picking out and understanding key words and topics. Diagrams and graphs are worth paying attention to at this level of reading the document. It is only worthwhile to study the material when you require in-depth understanding of a subject. It's recommended to scan the content first to gain a sense of the topic. This offers you a sense of its structure, into which you may put the information gleaned via a thorough, receptive reading.

3. Active Reading

Where you are reading a document in detail, it often helps if you highlight, underline and annotate it as you go on. This emphasizes in your mind, and helps you to review important points later. Doing this also helps to keep your mind focused on the material and stops it wandering.

This is obviously only something to do if you own the document. If you own the book and find that active reading helps, then it may be worth photocopying information in more expensive texts. You can read and mark the photocopies. If you are worried about destroying the material, ask yourself how much your investment of time is worth. If the advantage you obtain from active reading outweighs the book's cost, the book is considered trash.

4. How to learn various types of material

There are various locations and methods for storing various types of information.

They also differ in terms of coverage depth and breadth.

You can extract relevant information far more efficiently if you grasp the layout of the stuff you're reading.

Moreover, Pinnel, Su, and Fountas (1996, 22-23), argue that there are four techniques to gain reading proficiency in ELT: reading aloud, shared reading, guided reading, and independent reading.

Some details should be provided in order for pupils to gain a better understanding.

5. Reading 'Whole Subject' Document

It is simple to accept the writer's conceptual structure when reading an essential document. This means you can miss critical details that have been left out or unnecessary details that have been included. Making your own table of contents before opening the paper is an excellent approach to spot this. The table of contents can then be used to read the document in the order that you wish. You'll be able to detect errors immediately.

6. Using glossaries with technical documents

If you're reading a lot of technical content, photocopying or compiling a glossary might be helpful. As you read, keep this next to you. It will almost certainly be beneficial to write down the essential themes in your own words and refer to them as needed.

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1. Reading aloud.

A text is read aloud to students by the teacher or tutor.

This allows tutors to model reading, engage students in a material that they may not be able to read on their own, and allow students to relax and enjoy the story.

2. Shared reading

Tutors and students read together in Shared Reading, allowing students to actively participate and assist one another throughout the process.

To improve word recognition, tutors point to text as they read.

Tutors also read slowly to help students develop a sense of story.

3. Guided reading

Guided reading teaches students methods that will help them read independently in the future.

Tutors use guided reading to construct lessons that go beyond the story.

These courses put students to work on a variety of skills, including vocabulary development, character comparisons, story structure similarities, and linking literature to personal experience, among others.

The idea is to teach tutees skills that they can use on their own.

4. Independent reading.

Even those who believe in transactional definitions of literacy encourage pupils to read independently since effective independent reading skills will help them thrive in school.

Students read independently or in groups, select their own texts, and apply methods gained in previous reading exercises.

Conclusion. Reading, as one of the language skills, plays a critical part in achieving language proficiency. Many scholars explore the finest tactics to apply in reading activities, therefore it has modified its strategies throughout time. Reading activities, according to Luis (2007, 3), contain a variety of strategies and techniques that students can employ to improve their reading skills.

These are the following: 1) Knowing what you need to know and reading what you need to learn 2) Knowing how to read a document thoroughly; skimming, scanning, or studying 3) To pick out crucial ideas and keep your mind focused on the information, employ active reading techniques. 4) Reading periodicals and newspapers using the table of contents and clipping essential items 5) Understanding how to pull data from various sorts of articles, 6) Creating a table of contents for material review and 7) Using table of contents indexes and glossaries to assist students in assimilation of technical information. Reading aloud, Shared reading, guided reading, and independent reading are other four types of reading.

There are benefits and drawbacks to using those tactics.

The benefits of using these tactics include instilling a drive in pupils to read more, as well as creating an engaged classroom in which students can hear the teacher's voice while he reads aloud and then rush to the correct pronunciations.

However, these tactics have drawbacks, such as trouble achieving student reading comprehension since students are focused on reading the material effectively without understanding their needs or reading appropriately.

However, there are other ways that can be used to reach the goal of reading comprehension. The tactics listed above represent only a small portion of the strategies discovered by numerous writers. Although they have some advantages and downsides, they should be used based on the needs of the students and the classroom environment.

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